

The End of Euler Proof of Cubic Fermat Last Theorem

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Abstract: Euler's infinite descent proof of the conjecture that the cubic Fermat equation has no integer solutions has dominated the field for nearly three hundred years. However, the introduction of the principle of logical entropy reveals the deep logical flaws hidden in Euler's theory. Further research shows that Euler's proof only considers one special case among many possible scenarios. In fact, there are enough counterexamples that were obscured by Euler's clever statement. This marks the end of Euler's infinite descent proof of the cubic Fermat's Last Theorem.

Keywords: Fermat's equation; Fermat's last conjecture; Euler's infinite descent; logical entropy; logical entropy principle.

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1 Introduction

In the 17th century, French mathematician Pierre de Fermat conjectured that the equation $x^n + y^n = z^n$ has no integer solutions when the positive integer $n > 2$. This conjecture is called Fermat's Last Theorem^[1-6]. Fermat himself claimed to have a correct and wonderful elementary proof, but did not leave any details. There is no sufficient reason to confirm or deny the existence of the elementary proof. The proof of Fermat's Last Theorem puzzled mankind for more than 300 years until Andrew Wiles gave a recognized proof using complex modern mathematical tools in 1994^[7,8]. Wiles' proof relied on advanced elliptic curve theory and modular forms, which are beyond the understanding of ordinary mathematicians and mathematics enthusiasts. Historically, many mathematicians have used elementary mathematical tools to successively prove Fermat's Last Theorem for specific exponents. We have examined the details of some elementary proofs, such as Euler's infinite descent method for Fermat's Last Theorem with exponent 3^[9], but obtained a negative conclusion.

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2 Euler's proof of the Fermat's Last Theorem for cubes

The basic proof method of Fermat's Last Theorem is proof by contradiction. Assuming that the cubic Fermat equation $x^3 + y^3 = z^3$ has integer solutions, we usually consider the reduction of the equation, so the three integers x , y and z must be two odd numbers and one even number. Let's assume that x and y are odd numbers. Euler introduced coprime and it can be proved that u and v are represented by even number u and odd number v respectively, so that $x = u + v$ and $y = u - v$, and substitute them into the cubic Fermat equation to obtain the equivalent equation.

$$z^3 = 2u(u^2 + 3v^2) \quad (2.1)$$

Because the even number u and the odd number v are coprime, the above equivalent equation requires that $2u$ and $u^2 + 3v^2$ are both perfect cubic numbers, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 2u &= r^3 \\ u^2 + 3v^2 &= s^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

Where r is an even number, s is an odd number, and $\gcd(r, s) = 1$. The second equation is called Euler's nonlinear Diophantine equation. Euler gave the ternary array of this nonlinear Diophantine equation as

$$\begin{aligned} u &= e(e^2 - 9f^2) \\ v &= 3f(e^2 - f^2) \\ s &= e^2 + 3f^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Where e is an even number, f is an odd number, and $\gcd(e, f) = 1$. Substituting the above expression for u into the first equation in (2.2) yields

$$r^3 = 2u = 2e(e^2 - 9f^2) = 2e(e - 3f)(e + 3f) \quad (2.4)$$

Where $\gcd(2e, e - 3f) = \gcd(2e, e + 3f) = \gcd(e - 3f, e + 3f) = 1$. If equation (2.4) holds, there must exist even numbers k , odd numbers m , and odd numbers l that are coprime with each other,

$$\begin{aligned} 2e &= k^3 < r^3 < z^3 \\ e - 3f &= m^3 \\ e + 3f &= l^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Obviously $2e = (e - 3f) + (e + 3f)$, which leads to a smaller integer cubic Fermat equation,

$$k^3 = m^3 + l^3$$

The conclusion is that the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a hypothetical integer solution to the cubic Fermat equation is a smaller integer solution to the cubic Fermat equation, which constitutes a logical loop and cannot find the minimum integer solution. This is Euler's infinite descent method. Euler considered the case of $3|u$, and the logic is similar, so it is omitted.

3 The defects of Euler's infinite descent method

The key to Euler's infinite descent method is the construction of solutions for Euler's nonlinear Diophantine equations. Euler constructed a triplet, but did not explain the construction process of this triplet, thus hiding the question of whether the constructed solution is complete. If the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation has integer solutions that are not included in the Euler

triplet, then the Euler triplet is a partial solution of the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation. Furthermore, if the constructed solutions outside the range of Euler triplets do not possess infinite descent characteristics, then the Euler infinite descent method to prove the cubic Fermat's Last Theorem is invalid.

Let us calculate the specific values of the Euler triple (2.3) for $f = 1$, see Table 1. Then let us calculate the value of u corresponding to the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation (2.2) when $f = 1$ and $v = s$, see Table 2. Comparing the two tables, it is obvious that there are infinitely many integers u that are not included in the Euler triple. This proves that the Euler triple is only a partial solution of the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation.

Table 1: Euler triples for Euler's nonlinear Diophantine equations

e	f	$s = e^2 + 3f^2$	$u = e(e^2 - 9f^2)$	$v = 3f(e^2 - f^2)$	$u^2 + 3v^2 - s^3$
2	1	7	-10	9	0
4	1	19	28	45	0
6	1	39	162	105	0
8	1	67	440	189	0
10	1	103	910	297	0
12	1	147	1620	429	0
14	1	199	2618	585	0
16	1	259	3952	765	0
18	1	327	5670	969	0
20	1	403	7820	1197	0
22	1	487	10450	1449	0
24	1	579	13608	1725	0
26	1	679	17342	2025	0
28	1	787	21700	2349	0
30	1	903	26730	2697	0
32	1	1027	32480	3069	0
34	1	1159	38998	3465	0
36	1	1299	46332	3885	0
38	1	1447	54530	4329	0
40	1	1603	63640	4797	0
44	1	1939	84788	5805	0
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Table 2: Non-Eulerian triples for Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation

e	f	$s = e^2 + 3$	$v = s = e^2 + 3$	$u = \sqrt{s^3 - 3v^2}$	$u^2 + 3v^2 - s^3$
2	1	7	7	14	0
4	1	19	19	76	0
6	1	39	39	234	0
8	1	67	67	536	0
10	1	103	103	1030	0
12	1	147	147	1764	0
14	1	199	199	2786	0
16	1	259	259	4144	0
18	1	327	327	5886	0
20	1	403	403	8060	0
22	1	487	487	10714	0
24	1	579	579	13896	0
26	1	679	679	17654	0
28	1	787	787	22036	0
30	1	903	903	27090	0
32	1	1027	1027	32864	0
34	1	1159	1159	39406	0
36	1	1299	1299	46764	0
38	1	1447	1447	54986	0
40	1	1603	1603	64120	0
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

The non-Euler triples calculated in Table 2 that satisfy the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equations negate the completeness of the Euler triples. The Euler constructed solution of the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equations cannot contain all solutions. Whether the non-Euler triples that actually exist have the infinite descending characteristics that meet the proof of the third-order Fermat's Last Theorem, these simple and basic questions have been ignored for nearly 300 years, reflecting the potential bias in the development of mathematics and science. The values in Table 2 correspond to a non-Euler triple,

$$\begin{aligned}
 s &= e^2 + 3 \\
 v &= e^2 + 3 \\
 u &= e(e^2 + 3)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Substituting the expression of u into the first equation in (2.2) yields,

$$r^3 = 2u = 2e(e^2 + 3) \quad (3.2)$$

It can be proved that $\gcd(2e, e^2 + 3) = 1$, so the Diophantine equation (3.2) requires $2e$ and $e^2 + 3$ to be perfect cubic numbers. Obviously, the result cannot form a cubic Fermat equation with smaller integers, and the infinite descent method is invalid. The non-Euler triples of Euler's nonlinear Diophantine equations deny the universality of Euler's infinite descent proof of the cubic Fermat's Last Theorem. To deny a theory, one and only one counterexample is needed. It is no longer important whether there are many non-Euler triples of Euler's nonlinear Diophantine equations that have or do not have the Euler infinite descent feature.

4 Conclusion and comments

In summary, the infinite descent method of constructing the cubic Fermat's Last Theorem from Euler's partial solution of the Euler nonlinear Diophantine equation is not universally applicable, and the simplest case of Fermat's Last Theorem with an exponent of 3 has not yet been rigorously proven in elementary mathematics.

Euler's proof of Fermat's Last Theorem has had an absolute dominance for nearly 300 years. This incident shows that the reality is that even the incorrect logical deduction and inference of simple theories are rarely questioned because of the lofty status of the founders, which is regarded as absolute truth. This may lead to the neglect of logical defects in natural science that could have been solved.

Generally speaking, mathematical theories are very rigorous, but the theory of nonlinear Diophantine equations and partial differential equations are exceptions. The lack of systematic theory^[10] of nonlinear Diophantine equations is the fundamental reason why it is difficult to find a reasonable proof of Fermat's Last Theorem in elementary mathematics. The discovery of entangled spherical harmonics proves that the traditional theory constructs exact solutions to partial differential equations, and there are infinitely many exact solutions that are missed^[11-15]. The conclusions of natural science brought by incomplete inferences of basic mathematics are likely to be untrue. The relationship between the data, experimental principles and interpretation of the data in the experimental report becomes blurred, and scientific reports exceed scientific norms.

The similarity between Diophantine equations and partial differential equations is that equations can have constructed solutions, but the constructed solutions are not necessarily complete. Therefore, before the completeness of the constructed solutions of the equations is proven, it may not be appropriate to use the constructed solutions of the equations to further establish new theories and declare that the inferences have been experimentally verified. The confidence of the conclusions promoted by abstract language will eventually return to the original value.

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